

BRIDGING EUROPE AND ASIA: MUSIC AND DANCE-SCAPES ALONG THE SILK ROAD

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Abstract

The ancient Silk Road formed an intercontinental network connecting Europe and Asia, enabling vibrant exchanges of goods, ideas, and cultural traditions across Eurasia. During the Middle Ages, it extended from Asia to Anatolia and from Thrace to Europe. A significant impact of this movement was the transfer of performing art styles, resulting in rich and complex adaptations across the interconnected nodes of the vast network in a multidirectional flow of cultural transmission, profoundly impacting cultures and societies globally.

Building on existing scholarship on music and dance-scape, this paper examines the visualization, vocalization, and historicization of Silk Road performing art traditions in both classical and modern contexts. It explores textual production and the cultivation of literary and musical tastes through selected poetry and lyrics. Through an ethno-poetic lens, it analyzes the performative processes of literary samples, reading them not only as performances but as textual performances and cultural phenomena. The case studies present historically and discursively formed frontier and metropolitan cultures along the Silk Road—a literary topography created from time, space, cultural agents, signs, and metaphors.

Ethnomusicologists and dance scholars have drawn inspiration from cultural anthropology, approaching music and dance as products of human activities. While music, or in this case, "soundscape" emerged in the late 1960s and early 1970s as an auditory environment emphasizing individual and societal perception, "dance-scape" refers to an interconnected discourse of dance that accommodates cultural differences in dance historiography. By examining music and dance-scapes as dynamic embodiments of cross-cultural pollination catalyzed by the Silk Road, this research illuminates the intermingling of aesthetic modes that reverberated across the Eurasian realm over millennia. It demonstrates how the flourishing of art and culture was driven by the circulation of customs, motifs, and conventions along these ancient trans-continental conduits of exchange, highlighting the performing arts as evidence of how diverse aesthetic sensibilities converged and fused at vital cultural hubs.

Keywords: Eurasia, Silk Road, music and soundscape, dance, poetry, cultural exchanges, expressive arts.